

MANAGERIAL CHALLENGES REGARDING THE PROVIDING OF ESSENTIAL SERVICES WITHIN THE INSECURITY GLOBALIZATION CONTEXT

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Abstract

Purpose – Organizational resilience is a topical issue today, which deserves an interdisciplinary investigation aimed at the identification of the best intervention solutions to improve managerial processes and the situation of the organization as a whole. Things are all the more relevant when it comes to systems of services essential for the organization's functionality: the supply of electricity to consumers, the transportation of goods, payment services, the production of medicines, public services for emergency medical assistance, etc. What is the intensity and magnitude by which the (systemic, technical and operational) management of essential services will change over the next period, considering the manifestation of some crises and, especially, of the pandemic crisis? Can we identify lessons learned in the past that are similar in terms of the potential for change in management? What is the role of digitization and digitization in this framework?

Methodology/approach - The research methodology focuses on the consultation of recently developed literature to capture the trends manifested as possible paradigm directions in the development of management, in the context of the disruptive events affecting regions, continents or the entire world.

Findings – Under these conditions, the managerial systems are forced to place more emphasis on flexibility, by incorporating adequate information technologies. It is expected that the organization's resistance to change itself will alter, with obviously different intensities at individual or organizational level, as the robustness of organizations in the pre-crisis situation has mainly favored stability.

Research limitations/implications – The specific aspects of the pandemic crisis are still ongoing, with no known paradigmatic scientific approaches.

Practical implications – Of the specific processes of globalization, the one related to the security of individuals, organizations and, implicitly, of specific activities was selected. The challenge for political, economic, military decision makers, etc. is highest when the insecurity has regional or continental implications and consequences (example: the limitation of the free movement of people and goods). There is also an urgency to restore the normal functioning of the systems providing essential services.

Originality/value – This article brings to attention some managerial trends already manifested during the crisis generated by Covid 19. Interdependent and possible evolutionary trends are presented.

Key words: crisis, essential services, resilience.

Introduction concerning crisis management and organizational resilience

This study draws attention to crisis situations closely related to the essential services for the proper functioning of society, already manifested during the pandemic caused by Covid 19. The growing threat generated by Covid 19 affects the management processes and the organization as a whole. Therefore,

the aim is to find the best recommendations and intervention solutions for improvement and adaptation in the new pandemic context.

The term "crisis" is hotly debated and there are many definitions of crisis. Starting from the topic of this article, we will embody the notion of crisis as follows: (1) "an event or set of circumstances threatening the integrity, reputation or very existence of the individual or organization" (Sapriel, 2003, p.1); (2) an event or series of specific, unpredictable, out-of-routine events that create uncertainty and threat or are perceived as threatening an organization's highest priority goals (Ulmer, Sellnow and Seeger, 2017). Consequently, "crises appear as phenomena that can cause damage to an organization, both in terms of material losses and in terms of social prestige" (Sanda and Enea, 2014, p. 278).

Therefore, crisis management is defined as a specific administrative activity during the crisis state of the organization. In times of crisis in an organization, the main goal is to manage and improve the activities of the organization by taking measures to overcome the negative phenomena in the production and service of the entire organization or its components (Kazeem, 2009). Specialized literature captures various aspects regarding managerial processes in crisis situations. According to a recent research, the following steps are presented: (1) crisis reduction stage, (2) crisis preparedness stage; (3) crisis response stage; (4) crisis recovery stage (Fung, Tsui and Hon, 2020). The Crisis Management TEAM (CMT) consists of intergovernmental and inter-organizational networks that are called upon to respond to a crisis (Wester, 2011).

In order to effectively cope with the Covid 19 health crisis, the need for resilience is active in order to best "capitalize on the opportunities it presents, needing appropriate (and often new) organizational capabilities, innovation and entrepreneurship" (Liu, Lee and Lee, 2020, p, 278). "Resilience has become increasingly important for individuals, organizations and society in order to thrive in the uncertain, risky, hectic and ambiguous world we live in today" (van der Vegt et al., 2015, p. 974). To successfully manage and combat a global health crisis, resilience is needed both through psychological training and through organizational and system-level training support. A vital aspect of resilience is the cultural differences that "need to be carefully examined and incorporated into the design of any intervention aimed at strengthening resilience at the level of individuals, organizations and society in general" (Liu, Lee and Lee, 2020, p, 279).

Materials and Methods

In what regards essential services, the relevant national legislation, in accordance with the well-known NIS Directive ("EU Directive 2016/1148 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 July 2016 on measures for a high common level of security of networks and information systems in the Union" (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu>)), with specific address for essential service operators (ESO) in 7 sectors of economic activity: "energy, transport, banking, financial market infrastructure, health sector, drinking water supply and distribution, digital infrastructure" (Andersson, Charrie and Treeck, 2018, p. 10) and for Digital Service Providers (DSP) from three categories (online markets, online search engines, cloud computing services), specifies the conditions under which a service is considered essential, as follows: the service is essential in supporting the most important societal and / or economic activities; its supply depends on a network or computer system; the provision of the service is significantly disrupted in the event of an incident. Therefore, in this article we will conceptually use the essential notion in the extended sense, that of critical service.

Currently, the new crisis we are facing is caused by Covid 19. In December 2019, a severe acute respiratory infection caused by the new Covid 19 began to spread from Wuhan throughout China (Li Q., et al., 2020), and then affected the entire world (World Health Organization, 2020a). In the context of the Covid 19 pandemic, when an epidemiological outbreak threatens to have an impact on global economies and reputations, we find a global response through the overall link between the public health, science, politics, society and media sectors (McCloskey and Heymann, 2020). Therefore, communication plays an important role in the crisis management of essential services (Schultz, Utz and Göritz, 2011). This Covid 19 emerged so quickly that most organizations did not have time or had very little time to establish a strategy on how to run managerial processes in a crisis situation (World Health Organization, 2020b). Therefore, the main objective of each organization is to ensure that all employees, customers, suppliers, collaborators, etc. are informed about the real situation of Covid 19 and that important information is not missing. Organizations must also ensure that they take responsibility

following the advice of medical professionals and that activities continue to operate as smoothly as possible (Sohrabi et al., 2020).

Closely related to the pandemic evolution, managerial trends are heading towards the creation of a crisis plan on good management for the company's functionality. At European level, the European Commission is coordinating the Covid 19 pandemic by taking firm action "to strengthen public health sectors and mitigate the socio-economic impact in the European Union" (European Commission, 2020a; 2020b). At the same time, the European Union is directly involved in the proper functioning of essential service systems of general interest throughout Europe for the proper functioning of the society, ensuring the continuation of professional activities such as: medicine production, public emergency medical services, critical staff for public utility services, etc. (European Commission, 2020c).

The psychological impact on human resources on the Covid 19 pandemic regime is a vital factor in crisis management (Hamouche, 2020). "This pandemic crisis highlights the need for managers to be educated on the principles of implementation science in order to be able to make evidence-based decisions through an integrated, multi-sectoral response, taking into account contextual factors affecting implementation. This approach is essential in developing appropriate preparedness and response strategies during the current and future threats" (Binagwaho, 2020).

As jobs around the world are affected, management systems need to adapt to this new situation and develop managerial trends in order to prevent the damage that Covid 19 virus can cause. When referring to damage, we are referring to both safety and security, as well as to the productivity of the entire workforce worldwide. As the Covid 19 crisis spreads globally, organizations around the world are testing their training in crisis management. Particular importance is given to the way of managing the services that are essential for the good functioning of the company and for supporting the critical infrastructure systems, becoming a framework support in the development of management in critical situations (Badea, Bucovețchi and Iancu, 2020).

Following an analysis of specialized literature regarding different ways of crisis management, a number of researches on the topic process were selected. This study provides a set of good practices on service systems essential for the proper functioning of society and the trends manifested in the development of management. These proposals provide a general crisis management framework and provide guidelines on how to properly manage a crisis "in the context of disruptive events" (Bonanno, 2008, p. 102) such as Covid 19.

One model for managing the activity of organizations generated by the pandemic is the Kurzarbeit model. This model is a combination of the employment contract that each employee has and technical unemployment. The main feature of the model is the flexibility of the employees' work schedule, given that their activity gradually returns, as they recover the other areas of the economy, on which the employing entities are dependent. This model applies individually to each company, department, per employee and per day, and offers additional benefits. It is a system that extends the standard unemployment insurance system in three ways: (1) allowing workers to work fewer hours and the state pays proportionately unpaid time; (2) in the current pandemic context, job retention is important, even if employers do not work at all, a benefit for both the employee and the employer when they start work again; (3) allowing more generous incomes than usual unemployment. In Europe, the main measure to help workers has been the introduction or expansion of job retention schemes inspired by the Kurzarbeit scheme. The SURE program has been approved at the level of the European Union. It is aimed to reimburse the expenses incurred by the states for the Kurzarbeit type measures (European Commission, 2020d). In Romania, the implementation of this model involves the subsidy by the Government of a part of the salaries for those workers whose employers have changed their work schedule from normal to part-time, due to the economic crisis (Emergency Ordinance no. 92/2020). The details of the algorithm differ from country to country, but the essential principle is the same: employees keep their employment contracts with employers and receive a small reduction in wages, and the government pays most or all of the costs to employers.

Since the beginning of the threat of the Covid 19 outbreak, Korea has been facing a huge crisis. For a period of time, it was the second largest country in terms of the number of confirmed cases. However, this country has managed to slow the spread and prevent a second wave of infections and turn the medical crisis into an opportunity. "The Korean government and businesses have developed a variety of innovative prevention measures and products, for example: population testing and testing kits that can be used worldwide. Korean producers have the chance to revalue and restructure global supply

chains in order to make them more sustainable. Both the government and business sectors see clear growth opportunities in non-contact industries, including telecommunications, online education and distance learning solutions" (Liu, Lee and Lee, 2020, p, 280). Organizations can improve their reputation and help mitigate the negative impact of the global health crisis by implementing corporate social responsibility initiatives. "In short, resilience, strategic agility and entrepreneurship will continue to play a key role in capitalizing on the value of these opportunities in order to overcome the crisis" (Liu, Lee and Lee, 2020, p, 280).

Faced with certain challenges and an uncertain set of risks posed by Covid 19, "leaders are concerned about how their organizations will be affected and what they need to do next" (Deloitte, 2020). According to Deloitte, there are five key leadership qualities in organizational resilience during the COVID-19 crisis. Regardless of the magnitude of the impact of the virus on an organization, and although organizations are at different stages in what concerns their approach of the pandemic, which makes the impact vary by geography and sector, leaders need to be genuinely empathetic, treating employees, customers and their wider ecosystems with compassion, being "able to stabilize their organizations to deal with the crisis while finding opportunities through a series of key actions" (launching and supporting a crisis control center), maintaining continuity and funding of the business), maintaining as much illustrative data, even though information may be partially correct, in order to take decisive measures, anticipating emerging business models, etc. (Deloitte, 2020). The McKinsey team recommends five behaviors to help leaders during the Covid 19 pandemic for a good management and rebuilding of organizations: organizing through a network of teams, displaying deliberate calm and optimism, making decisions against uncertainty, showing empathy, and effective communication (McKinsey & co, 2020).

In terms of the medical system, the Covid 19 pandemic "brings new challenges to health systems, even to well-developed ones" (Médecins Sans Frontières, 2020). In order to face these new challenges, it is vital to observe and also act based on the experience of the countries affected by this virus, for example Italy, China, etc. It is important for healthcare systems to adapt and implement strategies. The experience of organizations in supporting communities facing the Covid 19 pandemic recommends "the protection of front-line personnel as a first step in combating this outbreak. Thousands of them get sick in the affected countries, so keeping them safe and free of infections is essential. The next step is to realize that although hospitals are vital, home care and information are very important. In an outbreak, it is not recommended that attention be focused only on hospital care; GPs and family doctors have a key role to play, and the wider community must be taken into account. People in health care facilities are at huge risk of Covid 19, because older people are the most vulnerable and live in close contact in these facilities, so it is important to reorganize the way these centers are run" (Médecins Sans Frontières, 2020).

Following the launch of an appeal to all members of The Romanian Academic Society of Management (SAMRO), on what and how to proceed in the current conditions, especially for the contribution to shaping an effective and efficient post-crisis management in Romania (SAMRO, 2020), we highlight some answers that are closely related to the topic of this article: (1) a negative factor manifested in the countries affected by the pandemic is the lack of stocks of medical supplies needed by the first line of defense personnel, this having multiple consequences: at the level of the person (risk of personal infection, colleagues, family, friends) and at the level of health organization (medical staff removed from the activity, therefore reducing the functionality of the medical system); (2) digitization is necessary and requires training / development of skills to understand and work in the online environment, and new developments are expected in the intensification of digitization - there is a high probability that virtual / online learning will become a component of education in the near future; (3) the closure of schools and universities can have a long-term negative impact on students, with regard to the online teaching and assessment process, which will later reflect on the labor market both at individual level and society-wise.

This crisis also demonstrates the need for management to move from a quantitative to a qualitative approach, which is also "imposed" by the characteristics of the industrial revolutions (Figure 1), an aspect that must be corroborated with the tendencies of crises (almost regardless of type) to exceed local or regional borders. Concepts such as VUCA (volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity) demonstrate their paradigmatic value by determining the re-instrumentalization of management for an "open world" and the full incorporation of ideas of communities and citizens into management systems, ideas that were first circulated 10 years ago by the famous group by North American specialists, "Renegade Brigade".

Figure 1. Characteristics of industrial revolutions

Source: <https://stiintasitehnica.com/patra-revolutie-industriala-8-previziuni-despre-schimbarea-lumii/>

Discussion and conclusions

The global and interconnected nature of essential services presents an important risk in the pandemic context, and consequently requires a critical analysis followed by a series of proposals for sustainable management in order to have a low social, economic and environmental impact.

In this article, the crisis is presented as a significant threat to the basic processes and, implicitly, on managerial processes and can have negative consequences if not managed properly. In most cases, crises can create threats in three directions: public safety, financial loss, loss of reputation. The Covid 19 pandemic context unites all three threats that an organization may face. If the managerial processes are not managed correctly or in due time, the health of the employees and not only, can be endangered. This will immediately have a negative influence on the organization's reputation and bring about inevitable financial losses.

The implementation of advanced information technologies and digitized applications contributes to reducing the impact of the pandemic crisis in the sense of favoring communication and process management within critical service systems. The use of SCADA systems also favors the continuity of activities, allowing the reduction of the presence of staff at work.

The potential generated in the field of organizational learning must be also pointed out in the sense of identifying good practices and awareness of the usefulness of viable contingency plans, and implicitly of internalizing the values of standards in the field of security and business continuity.

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